

INTEGRATION OF COCOA POD ASH, POULTRY MANURE AND NPK 20:10:10 FOR SOIL FERTILITY MANAGEMENT – INCUBATION STUDY

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ABSTRACT

A laboratory incubation study to determine the rate of nutrient supply by poultry manure (0, 5 and 10 t ha⁻¹), cocoa pod ash (0, 5 and 10 t ha⁻¹), NPK 20:10:10 fertilizer (0 and 150 kg ha⁻¹) and their combinations on soil properties was conducted at Igunshin in the rainforest zone of Southwest Nigeria. The 10 treatments were arranged in completely randomized design with nine replications. The soil was slightly acidic, low in OM, N, P and K. The incubation study showed that the soils treated with poultry manure (P) rates, cocoa pod ash (C) rates and their combinations significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased soil pH over the control and NPK 20:10:10 fertilizer (F). When poultry manure was combined with NPK 20:10:10 fertilizer, the pH of the soil decreased as the incubation period progressed while the pH increased with combined cocoa pod ash and the mineral fertilizer at 90 days of incubation. The rate of decrease in soil pH was more pronounced in the soils treated with NPK fertilizer alone. Total OC, total N, exchangeable K and Mg significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased as the period of incubation increased in all the treatments compared with control. Cocoa pod ash rates and cocoa pod ash combined with NPK fertilizer increased exchangeable Ca as the period of incubation increased while poultry manure rates and its combinations with NPK fertilizer decreased at 90 days of incubation. Combined poultry manure and NPK fertilizer had the highest N and P while combined cocoa pod ash recorded the highest Ca, K and Mg. Combination of poultry manure with reduced level of mineral fertilizer or cocoa pod ash had positive effect on the acid soil and increased the rate of nutrient mineralization than the sole application of poultry manure or cocoa pod ash.

KEY WORDS: Cocoa pod ash, poultry manure, integration, mineral fertilizer

INTRODUCTION

Recently research effort has shifted from single application of organic manures and mineral fertilizers to integrated plant nutrition management around the efficient use of low level of mineral fertilizer with organic manures in order to reduce the problems associated with sole use of mineral fertilizers and organic manures. In Nigeria, scarcity of mineral fertilizers, inefficient distribution channel and unjustly application without soil tests are major obstacles to the sole use of mineral fertilizers for optimum crop production. The acidic nature of these mineral fertilizers also poses threat to the tropical soils which are known to be acidic, fragile, kaolinitic and low in nutrient status. Organic manures on the other hand are bulky, low in nutrient quality, pose environmental health hazard and slow in mineralization hinder its sole use in soil fertility improvement.

Cocoa is widely grown in southwestern Nigeria and its husk is known to be rich in plant major and minor nutrients (Odedina, *et al.*, 2003 Ayeni *et al.*, 2008). It is advocated that cocoa husk be burnt to serve as farm sanitation. Also, its direct use as source of plant nutrients may lead to the spread of *Phytophthora palmivora* causing black pod disease of cocoa, thereby causing another problem for poor resource farmers. Transporting and milling large quantity of cocoa pod will also add to the farmers' cost of production. Burning of cocoa pod can serve as source of potash fertilizer (Adu-Dapaah *et al.*, 1994).

Poultry manure on the other hand, is widely used to serve as source of plant nutrients to supply N, P and micronutrients (Akanni and Ojeniyi, 2007), but; large quantity is needed to supply adequate of these nutrients to meet crop requirements. With boost in poultry companies in Nigeria, poultry litter is found in urban cities, that; constitutes nuisance and poses health hazards. Most farmers feel reluctant to use it to fertilize their farms because of the short falls.

Adeniyani and Ojeniyi (2006) have tested poultry manure combined with NPK fertilizer in experiments conducted on soil chemical properties, maize yield and nutrient uptake by maize in southwest Nigeria. Cocoa pod ash combined with NPK fertilizer (Ayeni *et al.*, 2008) has also been used in soil fertility management in southwest Nigeria. Cocoa pod is more available in Igunshin southwest Nigeria than poultry manure. Hence, its combined use with NPK fertilizer will be more beneficial to the poor resource farmers who see cocoa pods as waste products that need to be discarded than poultry manure combined with NPK fertilizer that is not as readily available as cocoa pod. This experiment aimed at comparing rate of nutrients release by combined application of poultry manure and NPK20:10:10 fertilizer with combined cocoa pod ash and NPK 20:10:10 fertilizer in Igunshin southwest Nigeria .

Table 1: Properties of poultry manure and cocoa pod ash used in the experiments (%).

Nutrient	OC	N	C/N	P	K	Ca	Mg	S
Poultry Manure	11.8	1.72	6.9	9.56	3.87	2.66	1.09	2.72
Cocoa pod ash	12.4	0.99	12.5	2.50	15.13	3.40	1.76	1.11

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Soil used for the laboratory experiment was collected from Igunshin in the forest zone (07° 05'N 04° 55') southwest Nigeria in early March 2007 and transferred to the Federal University of Technology Akure for nutrient analysis. Igunshin soil is derived from the basement complex rock (USDA Survey Staff, 1975) and is classified as Alfisol.

Soil analysis

Soil samples were taken from the site at 0-20cm depth for the experiment. The collected soil samples was air-dried and sieved through 2mm sieved mesh. Part of the soil sample was used for routine soil analysis and laboratory incubation study. Organic matter was determined by the dichromate oxidation method. Available phosphorus was extracted with Bray-1-P and determined colorimetrically (Bray and Kurtz, 1945). Exchangeable bases (Ca, K and Mg) were extracted with 1N ammonium acetate at pH 7.0. Potassium was read using flame photometer while Ca and Mg were determined on the atomic absorption spectrophotometer.

Analysis of poultry manure and cocoa pod ash

The nutrient composition of powdered poultry manure and cocoa pod ash were determined after ashing in a muffle furnace. With the exception of N, the determination of the organic materials was done using wet digestion method based on 25 – 5 – 5 ml of HNO₃ – H₂SO₄ – HCl₄ acids. Phosphorus was measured on spectronic 20 at 442(μm); K with photometer while Ca and Mg were determined with the use of AAS. Total N was determined with mickrokjedahl method.

Treatment Design and Application

Three levels of cocoa pod ash and poultry manure applied at 0, 0.25 and 0.5g/100soil to represent 0, 5 and 10 t ha⁻¹ and two levels of NPK 20: 10:10 fertilizer applied at 0 and 0.075g/100g soil to represent 0 and 150 kg ha⁻¹ were formulated to give ten treatments. The formulations and their abbreviations were: Absolute control (no treatment applied), 10 t ha⁻¹ poultry manure (P10), 5 t ha⁻¹ poultry manure (P5), 10 t ha⁻¹ cocoa pod ash only (C10), 5 t ha⁻¹ cocoa pod ash only (C5), 150 kg ha⁻¹ NPK 20:10:10 (F150), 10 t ha⁻¹ poultry manure combined with 150 kg ha⁻¹ NPK 20:10:10 (P10F150), 5 t ha⁻¹ poultry manure combined with 150 kg ha⁻¹ NPK 20:10:10 (P5F150), 10 t ha⁻¹ cocoa pod ash combined with 150 kg ha⁻¹ NPK20: 10: 10 (C10F150) and 5 t ha⁻¹ of cocoa pod ash combined with 150 kg ha⁻¹ NPK20: 10:10 (C5F150). Each treatment was put in a plastic cup, covered with a loosed asbestos sheet with equal amount of distilled water added weekly. The treatments were arranged in completely randomized design on a laboratory desk in a cool room. Each treatment was replicated nine times to give a total sum of ninety soil samples. Three samples of each treatment was chemically analyzed at 30 days interval and discarded.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The soil used for the experiment contained 1.29% OC, 0.10% total N, 5.97 mg kg⁻¹ available P, the exchangeable cations were 0.15, 2.32 and 0.30 cmol kg⁻¹ for available K, Ca and Mg respectively with pH of 6.09 (1:1 H₂O). The

soil was sandy clay. The initial soil characteristics showed that the soil was deficient N and P (Sobulo and Osiname, 1981). The chemical properties of the poultry manure and cocoa pod ash used in the experiment was shown in Table 1. Generally, poultry manure was richer in plant nutrients than cocoa pod ash except K and Ca.

Table 2: Effect of cocoa pod ash, poultry manure, NPK20:10:10 and their combination on soil pH and organic carbon

Treatment	60 days			60 days			
		pH			OC		
Control	6.06	6.08	6.03		1.32	1.37	1.39
F150	6.00	5.98	5.96		1.36	1.36	1.38
C5	6.38	6.52	6.99		1.33	1.39	1.43
C10	7.45	7.58	7.67		1.16	1.49	1.53
P5	6.20	6.29	6.17		1.38	1.59	1.60
P10	6.39	6.68	6.66		1.36	1.60	1.77
C5F150	6.22	6.29	6.48		1.38	1.52	1.69
C10F150	7.34	7.38	7.49		1.39	1.59	1.69
P5F150	6.17	6.2	6.09		1.48	1.65	1.97
P10F150	6.19	6.43	6.22		1.55	1.79	2.1
LSD (0.05)	0.18	0.2	0.23		0.07	0.09	0.09

F = NPK 20:10:10 fertilizer, C = cocoa pod ash, P = poultry manure

Application of poultry manure rate, cocoa pod ash rate and their various combinations had an immediate effect on pH of the soil used (Table 2). The pH of the soil samples treated with poultry manure, cocoa pod ash and their combinations were significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher than the control. Cocoa pod ash and poultry manure applied singly; and cocoa pod ash combined with NPK fertilizer (C5F150 and C10F150) increased soil pH as incubation period increased. NPK fertilizer applied singly decreased soil pH at 90 days of incubation. The decrease in pH of the soil samples treated with NPK 20:10:10 fertilizer compare with cocoa pod ash shows its acidifying effect. This might be as a result of its high ammonium content or acidulation of phosphate source used in formulation of the mineral fertilizer. Chude (1999) indicated that the phosphate source in the agro nutrient NPK fertilizer was about 25% acidulated.

The increases in pH of the soil samples treated with C5, C10, C5F150 and C10F150 show the liming effect of cocoa pod ash. Ayeni *et al.*, (2008a) observed similar increase in pH of soil treated with cocoa pod ash in the incubation experiment performed to show the effect of combined cocoa pod ash and poultry manure on soil chemical properties in Ondo southwest Nigeria. The decrease in pH of soil samples treated with poultry manure rates and its combination with NPK fertilizer compare with cocoa pod ash rates might be as a result of organic acids produced by poultry manure which also aided in acidifying the soil. Cocoa pod applied at 10 t ha⁻¹ had the highest liming effect as it recorded the highest pH (7.57) and Ca (6.70 c mol kg⁻¹).

Table 2 also shows the effect of cocoa pod ash, poultry manure, NPK20:10:10 fertilizer and their combinations on soil organic carbon within 90days of incubation. Decreases in OC in treatments C10 and P5F150 than the control at 30 days of incubation was observed (Table 2). Ano and Agwu, (2005), Machner and Nobel, (2002) observed similar decrease in soil organic carbon when an acid soil was incubated with organic materials and attributed the observation to increase microbial respiration stimulated by the added manure which might have caused temporary

immobilization. The OC in all the treatments increased through out the period of the experiment. The significance ($p < 0.05$) increase in the OC in the poultry manure and cocoa pod ash combined with NPK fertilizer rates compared with NPK fertilizer applied singly, indicates the ease with which mineralization takes place when the organic materials were combined with mineral fertilizer.

Cocoa pod ash rates, poultry manure rates, cocoa pod ash combined with NPK fertilizer and poultry manure combined with NPK fertilizer significantly increased soil total N, available P, K (except C5F150), Ca (except P10F150) as the period of incubation increased (Table 3). This shows continuous mineralization of the nutrient elements. F150 decreased total N, P and K (at 90 days) as the period of incubation increased. This shows that mineralization in NPK fertilizer had ceased before 90 days. NPK fertilizer applied singly had pH of 5.98, OC 1.36%, N 0.13%, P 6.97 mg kg⁻¹, S 6.97 mg kg⁻¹, exchangeable K, Ca and Mg 0.72, 0.85 and 0.45 cmol kg⁻¹ respectively. Cocoa pod ash rates had mean soil pH ranged 6.63 to 6.57, N 0.12 – 0.12%, P 6.76 – 7.59 mg kg⁻¹, S 11.06 – 12.55, K, Ca and Mg 2.01 – 2.52, 1.63 – 3.00, and 0.38 – 0.88 cmol kg⁻¹ respectively. Poultry manure rates had soil pH ranged between 6.22 – 6.58, OC 1.52 – 1.58, N 0.12 – 0.14%, P 7.40 – 13.96 mg kg⁻¹, S 13.11 – 35.98 mg kg⁻¹, K, Ca and Mg were respectively 1.74 – 1.89, 1.63 – 1.87 and 0.38 - 0.62. Cocoa pod ash (5 and 10 t ha⁻¹) combined with NPK fertilizer had the pH of 6.63 – 7.57, OC 1.38 – 1.39%, N 0.13 – 0.15%, P 7.59 – 10.19 mg kg⁻¹, S 17.00 – 24.84 mg kg⁻¹, K, Ca and Mg 2.33 - 2.55, 4.60 – 4.75 and 1.27 – 1.47 cmol kg⁻¹. Poultry manure rates (5 and 10 t ha⁻¹) combined with NPK fertilizer had soil pH of 6.15 – 6.28, N 0.13 – 0.16%, P 11.48 - 18.47 mg kg⁻¹, S 30.80 – 42.89 mg kg⁻¹, K, Ca and Mg 1.80 – 1.88, 1.66-2.41 and 0.47 – 1.35 cmol kg⁻¹ respectively. Compared with the nutrient critical level established for arable crops in southwest Nigeria, OM (3%), N 0.15%, P 8 – 10 mg kg⁻¹, 0.20, 0.24 and 0.16 cmol kg⁻¹ for K, Ca and Mg respectively, all the treatments supplied adequate nutrients except F150, C5 and P5. The control experiment had mean soil pH of 6.06, OC 1.36%, total N 0.11%, P 5 mg kg⁻¹, S 5mg kg⁻¹, K, Ca and Mg 0.50, 0.80 and 0.50 cmol kg⁻¹ respectively.

Treatment P10F150 had the highest N, P and S while C10F150 had highest K. Treatment C10 had the highest Ca value while C5F150 had highest Mg. This shows that integration of cocoa pod ash and poultry manure with NPK fertilizer enhanced nutrient release than sole application of any of the fertilizer materials. Phosphorus was found to be low in the soil treated with cocoa pod ash. The Phosphorus might have formed complex with soil Ca because P is known to form insoluble complex with Ca at pH above 7 (Busari *et al.*, 2004). This means, additional phosphatic fertilizer may be needed in order to correct P deficiency in the treatments that were low in available P i.e. C5, F150 and C5F150. The available K increased through out the period of incubation and was significantly higher than the absolute control. NPK 20:10:10 combined with poultry manure or cocoa pod ash increased the exchangeable Ca and Mg. The treatments with cocoa pod ash had higher increases in K, Ca and Mg. This confirms that cocoa pod ash is a source of K and Ca as indicated in the work of Adu-Dapaah *et al.*, (1994) and Ayeni *et al.*, (2008b). The higher cations released from combined cocoa pod ash than poultry manure indicates that the nutrients were released from cocoa pod ash included in the combination.

CONCLUSION

Combination of poultry manure with reduced level of mineral fertilizer or cocoa pod ash had positive effect on the acid soil and increased the rate of nutrient mineralization than the sole application of poultry manure or cocoa pod ash. It also made nutrient available in the soil within short time, thereby could enhance increase in production of crop with short life span. Poultry manure combined with NK20:10:10 fertilizer released more N, P and S than cocoa pod ash combined with NPK20:10:10 while combined cocoa pod ash and NPK 20:10:10 fertilizer released more K

Table 3: Rate of release of nutrients from cocoa pod ash, NPK fertilizer and their combinations within 90 days

Treatment	N			P			K			Ca			Mg			S		
	%			mg kg ⁻¹			-----cmol kg ⁻¹ -----			-----			mg kg ⁻¹					
DAYS	30	60	90	30	60	90	30	60	90	30	60	90	30	60	90	30	60	90
Control	0.10	0.11	0.11	4.40	5.02	5.10	0.50	0.53	0.59	0.76	0.77	0.79	0.36	0.40	0.60	4.28	5.00	6.00
F150	0.13	0.14	0.12	9.00	5.92	6.00	0.75	0.80	0.60	0.77	0.79	1.00	0.48	0.40	0.46	19.10	18.00	11.00
P10	0.10	0.15	0.16	13.42	13.65	14.80	0.62	2.45	2.60	0.70	2.40	2.51	0.22	0.40	0.53	17.00	21.90	69.05
C10	0.10	0.13	0.14	6.82	7.94	8.00	2.20	2.27	3.10	3.62	2.10	3.70	0.23	0.20	0.22	7.78	8.67	12.55
P5	0.11	0.12	0.14	6.45	7.73	8.02	0.54	2.30	2.38	1.45	1.70	1.73	0.24	1.20	0.43	6.56	10.10	22.66
C5	0.11	0.11	0.13	6.02	7.11	7.15	1.00	2.10	2.92	3.10	2.30	2.36	0.23	1.20	1.21	4.99	7.50	11.06
P10F150	0.13	0.18	0.18	18.00	18.52	18.90	1.52	1.92	2.20	1.90	2.90	2.44	0.26	1.90	1.90	24.44	32.24	72.00
C10F150	0.14	0.15	0.15	10.05	10.10	10.42	1.90	2.20	3.55	2.00	6.20	6.22	1.09	1.40	1.32	20.00	25.00	29.46
P5F150	0.13	0.14	0.13	11.23	11.40	11.80	0.93	1.98	2.48	1.50	1.70	1.79	1.00	0.20	0.21	20.61	12.80	59.00
C5F150	0.13	0.13	0.14	7.20	7.44	7.72	1.30	3.10	2.59	2.49	5.22	6.09	1.00	1.70	1.72	10.00	20.00	21.00
LSD	0.03	0.04	0.04	4.32	4.72	4.97	1.27	0.37	1.11	1.56	0.39	1.12	1.44	2.56	0.25	10.37	2.77	27

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